

Effect of Meaning and Accuracy Model Approach on the Grammar Proficiency of Grade 4 Learners

Amy R. Araneta

Abstract. This study sought to determine the effect of Meaning and Accuracy Model, on the grammar proficiency of grade four learners. Method used was quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. This study was conducted in Binugao Cenprtal Elementary School, Binugao District, Division of Davao City. The respondents of this study were the 83 grade four learners – 42 are from section A which was the controlled group and 41 are from section B which was the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades and was made of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher had met the learners online for a follow up session of what has been printed in the module. This study revealed that the utilization of Meaning and Accuracy Model has increased the grammar proficiency of grade four learners. It was also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. Meaning and accuracy model approach
2. grammar proficiency
3. grade 4 learners

Date Received: May 21, 2024 — Date Reviewed: May 23, 2024 — Date Published: June 5, 2024

1. Introduction

Teaching grammar is an essential aspect of your role as a language teacher. Your students rely on you to provide them with the tools necessary to engage in conversations with others, and grammatical structures make up much of the linguistic toolbox. But teaching English grammar can seem like a daunting task, perhaps even a little dry, especially when you've been doing it for years. Maybe it's time to breathe a bit of new life into your lessons with these strategies for teaching grammar to English language learners. Teaching grammar to English learners requires a balanced approach that combines explicit instruction with contextual learning. It's essential to start with clear explanations of grammatical rules, supported by numerous examples and practice exercises to reinforce understanding. Integrating grammar instruction with reading, writing, speaking, and listening activities helps students see how grammar functions in real-life contexts. Using inductive learning strategies, where students discover rules through pattern recognition and hypothesis testing, can enhance their grasp of

grammar. Additionally, employing technology and interactive tools such as educational software, online resources, and games can make learning more engaging. Regular review, constructive feedback, and practical application in meaningful contexts are crucial for reinforcing grammar skills. Patience and encouragement from the teacher play a vital role in building student confidence and facilitating a supportive learning environment (Butler, 2021). Incorporating games into grammar instruction can be incredibly effective and engaging. You can use games to introduce new structures, reinforce what you've just examined, or both! Consider games like Board Race that utilize TPR (Total Physical Response) to aid in retention and burn a bit of extra energy. Thus, teaching grammar is enjoyable and not exhausting (Verma,2020). If there's anything that can be said with certainty, it's that young learners need frequent stimulation to sustain engagement. Here are some ideas to fulfill this need when teaching English grammar. Take advantage of your students' innate music memory and use songs for teaching English grammar. It's hard to teach grammar when teacher does not used effective strategies (Barajas,2020). Visuals can serve as wonderful aids to teach English grammar, spelling out rules for students explicitly (deductive teaching), demonstrating the use of a particular structure in context, and asking students to notice structures and draw their own conclusions about the rules (inductive teaching) (Bikowski,2021). If a deductive approach is used, show your students a simple chart with two columns for the simple present and the simple past tenses. You'd explicitly tell students that when a verb is regular in the present tense, you simply add an -ed (or just the -d, if the base form ends in "e") to make it past tense (Widodo,2022). On the other hand, an inductive approach might be that you showcase sets of images with short sentences underneath narrating what's happening in the images. For example, the first picture in a set might show little Sara sitting contentedly with a scoop of ice cream, with the subtitle "Sara likes ice cream." The second picture in the set might show little Sara again, this time with ice cream all over her face and an empty bowl. She has a satisfied grin on her face and the subtitle reads "Sara liked her ice cream a lot." Students would see that the past tense is indicated by the -ed ending. This confuses learners to learn grammar in English (Neumann,2022). In the division of Davao City particularly in Binugao Central Elementary School, teachers also experienced difficulty in teaching grammar. Learners found out that grammar lesson to be boring and so teachers need strategies that would tickle the interest of the learners during teaching grammar. Hence, this study was conducted.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

$$O_1 \quad x \quad O_2$$

$$O_3 \quad x \quad O_4$$

Where:

O_1 – Pretest of the experimental group

O_2 – Posttest of the experimental group

O_3 – Pretest of the controlled group

O_4 – Posttest of the controlled group

--- - Non-random assignment of subjects

X – Treatment applied in the experimental group

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study was conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School, Binugao District, Division of Davao City. The subjects of this study were the 83 grade four learners – 42 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 41 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	No. of Pupils	Count
Section A		42
Section B		41
Total		83

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher had met the learners online for a follow up session of what has been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 45 –item test eventually determined the grammar proficiency of the research subjects. The pretest was administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest was very helpful to assess the grammar proficiency of the grade four learners. On the hand, post test was also administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the grammar proficiency of the grade four learners, the following continuum were used based on DepEd rating system.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Scale Criteria for Student Performance

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher had drafted a letter seeking for permission that this research study was conducted and were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, Dr. Reynante A. Solitario, CESO V and the school principal of Binugao Central Elementary School. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and had it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study

be conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher administered pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered the posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects was submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean used to describe the level of the grammar of the grade

four learners in both pretest and posttest scores. Eta square used to measure the magnitude of meaning and accuracy model on the grammar proficiency of grade four learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade seven learners. The controlled group got the mean of 53.77 or

Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 56.24 or Beginning.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	<i>n</i>	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	45	24.20	53.77	Beginning
Experimental Group	45	25.31	56.24	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Pellas (2019) who said that students who exhibit a higher level of self-confidence show an increased willingness to

actively participate in online learning activities, demonstrate proactive behavior, and exhibit resilience as they deal with obstacles, particularly in situations where students are more vulnerable to experiencing stress in online learning. Students who had a strong belief in their own capabilities to achieve success demonstrated a

greater aptitude to establish challenging goals, engage actively in discussions, and maintain a firm belief in their ability to overcome challenges. The utilization of a question-and-answer technique promotes active student participation through the establishment of an interactive learning environment. Students experienced a heightened sense of autonomy, which facilitated their active engagement in the learning process through the expression of their thoughts, questions, and asks for further elaboration. Consequently, this fosters a greater level of participation and motivation among students (Poot, 2020). In addition, students who actively participate in classroom discussions through question-and-answer sessions demonstrate higher levels of engagement and motivation. This increased engagement leads to enhanced academic outcomes and performance (Pashler, 2021). Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade four learners. The controlled group got the mean of 36.11 or developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 38.10 or Ap-

proaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 12.79 from a mean rating of 25.31 to 38.10. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of King (2019) who cited that the utilization of the question-and-answer method in classrooms fosters an environment conducive to active learning. This instructional technique necessitates students to engage in critical thinking, retrieve information from memory, and effectively express their views and ideas. Through active engagement in classroom discussions, students are able to cultivate a more profound comprehension of the subject matter. Moreover, this method encourages students to think critically about the subject matter and articulate their ideas precisely. Students develop their ability to analyze information and construct logical arguments through active participation in the Q and A method (Bjork, 2020).

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	<i>n</i>	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	45	36.11	80.24	Developing
Experimental Group	45	38.10	84.66	Approaching Proficiency

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.42 with a p-value of .0321 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade four learners. This implies that the used of Q and A approach have contributed to the self-confidence which is revealed by the scores of the grade four learners. This finding is in line with the statement of Yang (2019) who said research studies suggest that the establishment

of a positive learning environment is vital for fostering the development of confidence among learners. A classroom environment that fosters support and inclusivity, wherein students have a sense of value and respect, establishes a safe environment that encourages them to explore into new areas and actively participate in the learning process, free from fear of criticism or setbacks. This learning environment fosters a sense of self-efficacy among students and enhances their self-confidence. The use of questions and answers as a method enhances the relationship between teachers and students,

fostering a setting conducive to open conversation, mutual trust, and cooperative efforts. The perception of students is that the role of teacher is that of a facilitator of learning, rather than solely a provider of knowledge. In addition, this technique fosters an atmosphere of trust and mutual respect between teachers and students. When students have a sense of comfort in posing questions and engaging in active discussion, they cultivate a sense of connection with their teacher, thereby fostering enhanced motivation and academic success (Palmer, 2019).

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value
Pre-test and Post-test	38	-5.42	.0321

Note. df = degrees of freedom.

Table 4 highlights the test of Q and A approach on the self-confidence of Grade 4 students. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.351 which signifies large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in enhancing students' self-confidence of Grade 4 students. Confidence serves as a catalyst for academic achievement, social competence, resilience, and personal development. As educators and mentors, nurturing self-confidence in students should be a priority, fostering an environment that encourages growth, empowerment, and the realization of each student's full potential. The question-and-answer approach is helpful for teachers since it enables them to evaluate the understanding of students of the subject matter. By employing specific questions, teachers are able to assess the extent of understanding and pinpoint areas that require additional elaboration. This method of instruction facilitates educators in modifying their instructional methods to cater to the unique needs of their students (McDermott, 2020). However, it is crucial to acknowledge that the efficacy of the question-and-answer approach is dependent upon factors such as the teacher's adeptness in facilitating discussions and the entire environment within the classroom. The successful implementation of the QandA approach requires the utilization of efficient classroom management strategies. It is important for educators to make sure equal participation opportunities for all students, foster an atmosphere of respect and inclusivity, and effectively manage time to meet the planned curriculum. In addition, creating a safe and inclusive classroom environment encourages students to engage in QandA sessions without being afraid of ridicule or judgment (Zillmann, 2019).

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post-test Scores of the Grade 6 Students

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
45	-4.26	0.351	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Note. N = sample size.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of Meaning and Accuracy Model, on the grammar proficiency of grade four learners. Eventually, it also sought to determine the magnitude of effect of the action initiated by the researcher on the grammar proficiency of the research subjects.

4.1. Findings—This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School, Division of Davao City. The subjects of this study were the 83 grade four learners – 42 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 41 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

This study revealed that the utilization of Meaning and Accuracy Model approach had increased the grammar proficiency of grade four learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade four learners both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test

scores of the controlled group is at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching Proficiency.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching Grade 4 students should use Meaning and Accuracy model approach as a strategy that would further develop the self-confidence of learners in order to make the teaching and learning process meaningful. If learners take part in the learning process by active participation in unfolding of the lesson, then he will appreciate the concept being develop, thus, he is learning. The school heads should promote the use of Meaning and Accuracy model approach as a strategy that would engage the child actively in the learning process as it is revealed in the study that it is effective especially on subjects that are narrative in nature and are not interesting to learners. A school policy about the utilization of Meaning and Accuracy can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during LAC session using Meaning and Accuracy model approach as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of role play as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

- Al-Jarrah, R. S. (2021). A suggested model of corrective feedback provision. *Ampersand*.
- Amaratunga, D. (2020). Quantitative and qualitative research in the built environment: Application of ‘mixed’ research approach. *Work Study*.

- Angee, J. (2021). Developing qualitative research questions: A reflective process. *Int. J. Qual. Stud. Educ.*
- Barajas, C. (2020). Comprehension of texts by deaf elementary school students: The role of grammatical understanding. *Res. Dev. Disabil.*
- Becker, C. (2022). An approach to creative speaking activities in the young learners' classroom. *Educ. Inq.*
- Bernstein, B. (2020). *The structuring of pedagogic discourse: Class, codes and control* (Vol. 4). Routledge.
- Bikowski, D. (2021). Technology for teaching grammar.
- Butler, M. (2021). The implementation of communicative and task-based language teaching in the asia-pacific region. *Annu. Rev. Appl. Linguist.*
- Coppen, P. A., & Graus, J. (2020). The interface between student teacher grammar cognitions and learner-oriented cognitions. *Mod. Lang.*
- Curzio, J., & S., K. (2021). Integrating qualitative and quantitative research methods. *J. Res. Nurs.*
- El-dali, H. (2020). Towards an understanding of the distinctive nature of translation studies. *J. King Saud Univ. - Lang. Transl.*
- Ellis, R. (2020). The definition and measurement of l2 explicit knowledge. *Lang. Learn.*
- Farjami, F., & Aidinlou, N. A. (2022). Developing mixed methods crossover analysis approaches. *J. Mix. Methods Res.*
- Folse, E. R. (2021). When students tackle grammatical problems: Exploring linguistic reasoning with linguistic meta concepts in 11 grammar education. *Linguist. Educ.*
- Foster, I. (2020). The future of language learning. *Lang. Cult. Curric.*
- Jones, P., & Chen, H. (2020). The role of dialogic pedagogy in teaching grammar. *Res. Pap. Educ.*
- Kafipour, R. (2020). The effect of task-based language teaching on analytic writing in efl classrooms. *Cogent Educ.*
- Lin, H., & Lee, P. (2020). The effect of the inductive and deductive data-driven learning (ddl) on vocabulary acquisition and retention. *System.*
- Luciano, R. (2019). *Rousing minds to life: Teaching, learning, and schooling in social context*. Cambridge University Press.
- Nagy, W. E., Anderson, R. C., & Herman, P. A. (1987). Learning word meanings from context during normal reading. *American Education Research Journal.*
- Neumann, H. (2022). Teacher assessment of grammatical ability in second language academic writing: A case study. *J. Second Lang. Writ.*
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2019). From the community to the classroom: The impact of family involvement on language learning. *TESOL Quarterly.*
- Osa-Melero, L. (2021). The impact of the inductive approach on the learning of spanish. *Electron. J. Foreign Lang. Teach.*
- Rahman, Z. A. (2022). The use of cohesive devices in descriptive writing by omani student-teachers. *Int J Eval & Res Educ.*
- Richards, J. (2020). The changing face of language learning: Learning beyond the classroom. *RELC J.*
- Safford, K. (2020). Teaching grammar and testing grammar in the english primary school: The impact on teachers and their teaching of the grammar element of the statutory test in spelling, punctuation and grammar (spag). *Chang. English Stud. Cult. Educ.*

- Sargeant, J. (2020). Qualitative research part ii: Participants, analysis, and quality assurance. *J. Grad. Med. Educ.*
- Shadiev, R., & Yang, M. (2021). Review of studies on technology-enhanced language learning and teaching [Open Access Journal]. *Sustainability*.
- Sik, K. (2020). Tradition or modernism in grammar teaching: Deductive vs inductive approaches. *Procedia - Soc. Behav. Sci.*
- Smith, R. (2020). *Voices of the mind: The history of teaching english as a foreign language, from a british and european perspective*. Lang. Hist.
- Stocksloger, P. D. (2021). *Contextual teaching and learning: What is it and why is it here to stay* [A Sage Publication Company]. Corwin Press Inc.
- Tammenga, H. (2020). The effectiveness of deductive, inductive, implicit and incidental grammatical instruction in second language classrooms. *System*.
- Tavera, L. C., & Casinillo, N. (2020). Funds of knowledge for teaching: Using a qualitative approach to connect homes and classrooms. *Theory into Practice*, 58(6), 570–580.
- Tayjasanant, C., & Barnard, R. (2020). Language teachers' beliefs and practices regarding the appropriateness of communicative methodology: A case study from thailand. *J. Asia TEFL*.
- Tozcu, A., & Coady, J. (2019). Successful learning of frequent vocabulary through call also benefits reading comprehension and speed. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*.
- Ugla, R. L. (2020). The influence of proficiency level on the use and choice of 11/12 communication strategies used by iraqi efl students. *Int. J. Eval. Res. Educ.*
- Verma, A. (2020). Aligning sampling and case selection in quantitative-qualitative research designs: Establishing generalizability limits in mixed-method studies. *Ethnography*.
- Widodo, H. P. (2019). Approaches and procedures for teaching grammar. *English Teach. Pract. Crit.*